

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DEVELOPING THE ORAL DISCOURSE OF THE FOREIGN LANGUAGE OF THE STUDENTS (OF THE SPECIALTY) USING EDUCATIONAL SITUATIONS AND ROLE-PLAYING GAMES

Eshankulova Dilnoza Ramazonovna

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, Faculty of Foreign Languages and Literature, second stage master's student

Normatova Nurjamol Normatovna

Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences

ABSTRACT

The article discusses role-play as a methodological technique that belongs to the group of active ways of teaching practical knowledge of a foreign language. The basic didactic structures of role-plays are analyzed. And also main structural components of the teaching role plays are highlighted based on the main characteristic features of all role plays in language learning.

Keywords: role-play, teaching technique, flexibility, social skills.

INTRODUCTION

English becomes the most essential language in the world. Almost all the people from many different countries around the world use it to communicate. It's because of the importance of English in any field of our lives. Speaking is a language skill of oral communication to express human idea, feeling, opinion, and thought or information which helps people to communicate one another. Learning language does not mean just learning about structure or vocabulary but the important thing is learning how we use language for communication to one or the other person, how we speak and make the people understand what we talk. Furthermore, in developing speaking activity, the students need a good condition to increase their speaking frequency such as learner's language environment. Some teachers are unaware of the possibilities of role-play. They may feel that such an activity is not appropriate for classes which cause discipline problems and that conducting role-play would create chaos. In addition, they claim that students may be reluctant to be someone else, or, that their level of language is too low.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The didactic structure of the teaching role-plays is based on the theory of students' role-playing games.

According to D.B. Elkonin structure of the students' role plays consists of 4 elements: The roles that student take on;

Game actions and actions by which students realize their roles and relations between them in the general context of the game

Props of the game;

Real relations between playing students (remarks, comments, regulating the game). Having extensive experience in playing activities related to pleasant emotions, a teenager easily and with pleasure accepts a game during the educational process. As experience shows, in foreign language lessons, the game does not lose its attractiveness to students, although they, of course, are aware of non-game characters embedded in the role-playing game, i.e. training goals. However, for the teacher, the structure of the game is complicated precisely by the inclusion of educational tasks, as well as the creation of didactic conditions necessary to achieve game and educational goals.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main features of all role-plays are:

The existence of the problem underlying the game;

The presence of certain characters / roles that have a different relationship to the issue under discussion; The presence of a problematic situation that contains the conditions for cognitive conflict.

There are 5 main structural components of an educational role-playing game:

Goals (game and educational);

The content of the game (the language material of one or more conversational topics, a set of training situations);

A set of roles through which the game is realized; 4) the plot (script) of the game; 5) props.

Role-play in foreign language lessons is used primarily for the development of speaking skills and correlates with both forms of speech: prepared and unprepared, creating the prerequisites for the natural transition of the first to the second. This, in turn, presupposes the preliminary assimilation of linguistic material, the formation of appropriate skills and abilities, which ultimately allow students to focus on the substantive side of their statement. According to meet the needs of modern society requirements, young professionals should be goal-oriented, creative and energetic. They also bring a fresh perspective – a new look at old problems. The ability to communicate effectively in a foreign language is primary essential nowadays in the period of globalization. In recent years, there has been increasing demands for graduates

who know English or other foreign language well enough to be ready to use it in real life communication and speak confidently. Over the last decade, problems of overcoming language barriers in teaching a foreign language and making the teaching process more effective has gained much attention. Role playing is one of the large amount of drama activities which can be listed as a successful educational technique in the foreign language class because of presents some important characteristics for its teaching: easy organization, flexibility, it can be open ended, it's funny, it's a dress rehearsal for real life, it provides a lot of different experiences, it trains students to deal with some social skills of language and it helps in the memorization of new vocabulary, expressions and grammar. Making the students speak up in the EFL classroom and outside it is one of the big challenges for language teachers today. Their resistance in speaking usually comes from their fear of making mistakes and from exposing themselves to an audience. Role play can make the students get used to speaking and become, gradually, more confident and, consequently, more competent. Role play is one of a whole gamut of communicative techniques which develops fluency in language students, which promotes interaction in the classroom and which increases motivation. Not only is peer learning encouraged by it but also the sharing between teacher and students or the responsibility for the learning process. The frequent use of role play techniques in the classes may encourage students to speak and develop their oral skills. Role play provides enthusiasm in the classroom and, without enthusiasm in the classroom, learning becomes just a chore ... Combine enthusiasm with involvement and it would seem to lead to more interesting classes and more effective learning" In this article he quotes a Chinese proverb that says "Tell me and I forget; teach me and I remember; involve me and I learn" which can exemplify with success the function that the use of role plays have in class development. Another function of the use of role playing techniques is as a facilitator for the linguistic items memorization. Role play activities provide physical and visual reinforcement that increases involvement and helps to fix vocabulary, structure and grammar points in mind.

CONCLUSION

Language teaching can be an interesting challenge when teachers make the effort to explore a variety of approaches. Role play is just one of the many methods available for exploitation. With some attention given to the needs of the learners, both the teacher and the learners can play active roles in the classroom, making language classes livelier, challenging and above all rewarding. So, role play increases motivation. Always talking about real life can become very dull, and the chance to imagine different situations adds interest to a lesson. Role play gives a chance to use language in new contexts and for new topics. Again, role playing in itself is no panacea, any more than the new "scope" technologies now revolutionizing surgery can be

effectively applied by people with little training. These are tools, and in good hands, they can powerfully enhance the attainment of the teachers' goals. The movement towards social and emotional learning in the schools and the promotion of emotional intelligence also should make use of this valuable resource.

REFERENCES:

1. Zimnya I.A. "Psychology of teaching foreign languages at school". M., 2011. 273
2. Kalimulina O.V. Role-plays in teaching dialogic speech // Foreign languages at school, 2013. № 3. 183 p. .
3. Elkonin B.D. Psychology: textbook. Allowance for students. Higher institutions / ed. Comp. 4th ed. M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 2017. 384 p.
4. Ladousse Gillian Porter. Role Play: Resource Books for Teachers. Oxford, Oxford Press, 2017.
5. Maurice Keith. Laugh While Learning Another Language: Techniques That are Functional and Funny, 2018.